

Effectiveness of Multi-Media approach Instructional Package on the development of selected competencies in mathematics among slum students -An Experimental study

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ABSTRACT

UEE has been one of the most important goals of educational development in India since independence. Article 45 of the Constitution has directed the state to provide free and compulsory education to all children up to the age of 14 years within a period of ten years of the commencement of the constitution. To promote literacy among its citizens, Government of India has launched several schemes but it is a sad situation that the dropout rate in India is very high. Several reasons can be given for this state of affairs. A major portion of the dropouts consists of socially disadvantaged children. Most of the children have to work very hard to earn their livelihood, and live in slums.

Modern approaches in the education technology like multimedia applications using computer technology prove to cater to the diverse needs of students in the educational setup. Multimedia is a unique medium with features of quality, audio-visual recording, and sound effects. It can be conveniently used to convey well designed information with varying special effects. Students learn effectively through Multimedia Approach, which is perceptual learning (Andrew Laghos, 2010; Siew Pei Hwa, 2009; Eun Joon Um, 2008; Norhayati, A. M., and Siew, P. H., 2004 and others).

*The present study was carried out with the objective to study the effectiveness of the multi-media approach Instructional Package in relation to traditional approach in fostering **selected Mathematics Competencies** among Slum Students. The sample of the study was 40 slum students of standard six. The pre-posttest experimental design was followed for the present research study. The treatment for the Experimental group was given by the investigator for 40 sessions specifically to foster Mathematics Competencies using a specially designed instructional material. The obtained data were analyzed by using mean, S.D., t-test and ANCOVA. Analysis of the results revealed, that Multi-Media Approach Instructional Package was significantly more effective than of the traditional method in fostering selected Mathematics Competencies among Slum students. Multimedia approach can be followed to help students to foster their achievement level. Educational implications of the study were i) Teachers need to be trained to use multimedia approach rather than simple lecture demonstration method, ii) The teachers need to be trained to prepare instructional material based on multimedia approach, iii) The text books should give enough guidelines to help teachers to use multimedia approach for different topics of the syllabus.*

Key words: multi-media approach, slum students, mathematics competencies

INTRODUCTION

UEE has been one of the most important goals of educational development in India since independence. Article 45 of the Constitution has directed the state to provide free and compulsory education to all children up to the age of 14 years within a period of ten years of the commencement of the constitution. The revised policy stated that, "It shall be ensured that

free and compulsory education of satisfactory quality is provided to all children up to 14 years of age before enter the 21st century.”

To promote literacy among its citizens, Government of India has launched several schemes and one of the most fundamental and promising of these schemes is the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan and right to education. The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education (RTE) Act, 2009, which represents the consequential legislation envisaged under Article 21-A, means that every child has the right to full time elementary education of satisfactory and equitable quality in a formal school which satisfies certain essential norms and standards. Article 29 (2) lays down that “no citizen shall be denied admission into any educational institution maintained by the state or receiving aid out of state funds on grounds only of religion, race, caste, language or any of them.”

It is a sad situation that the dropout rate in India is very high. Several reasons can be given for this state of affairs. Education in India to a large extent is a question of choice rather than a priority. It is the choice between basic needs and intellectual growth, and naturally people give preference to the former. In many families, both the parents go out for work as result of which the eldest child and invariably the girl child is made to look after the younger siblings. Besides, on account of poverty the minor child is forced to supplement the income of the family leading to child labour. In other cases, parents cannot afford to provide the minimum requirements for their children to send them to school. A major portion of the dropouts consists of socially disadvantaged children. These children are the focus today; as they are the ones who come from very poor or semi-starving families, where the parents cannot provide even a single meal in a day for them. Most of the children have to work very hard to earn their livelihood, and live in slums. Slum education has remained an ignored sector of the human resource planning in India.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Researches on slum students and their level of education reveals a dire need for the education of slum students as well as a diversified and unique system of education for the slum students (Sveta Dave Chakravarthy, 2005). The low achievement is a matter of serious concern and needs special attention of the curriculum developers and translators. Low motivation of the teachers to teach the children of poor socio-economic background and low educational status of the mother could be another probable cause for the dropout (Samajik Suvidha Sangam Society 2009). Not finding a friendly environment in school, these children lose interest in studies and dropout.

Hence, modern approaches in the education technology like multimedia applications using computer technology prove to cater to the diverse needs of students in the educational setup. Multimedia is a unique medium with features of quality, audio-visual recording, and sound effects. It can be conveniently used to convey well designed information with varying special effects. Students learn effectively through Multimedia Approach, which is perceptual learning (Andrew Laghos, 2010; Siew Pei Hwa, 2009; Eun Joon Um, 2008; Norhayati, A. M., and Siew, P. H., 2004 and others). A combination of multimedia audio-visual teaching method used, with novelty, diversity and interest, can be entertaining, arousing student’s interest in learning.

Therefore, this multimedia approach has been followed in the preparation of lessons for the package. This package was used to develop the expected competencies.

Thus, the investigator deduced the results of Multimedia Approach through research studies and felt that this would appropriately fit in the context of education for slum children. Hence, the investigator attempted to validate the effect of Multimedia Approach on developing selected Competencies in Mathematics among slum children.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Effectiveness of Multi-Media Approach Instructional Package on the Development of Selected Competencies in Mathematics among the Slum students of standard six of Mysore District.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study whether there exists any significant difference between the pre-test scores of Slum students of experiment and the control group on Intelligence.
2. To study the effectiveness of the designed Instructional Package (Experimental treatment) in relation to traditional approach in fostering **selected Mathematics Competencies** among Slum Students after adjusting for the initial differences in Intelligence and Mathematical Reasoning.
3. To study whether there exists any significant difference between the mean scores of pre- test and post-test of the experiment group on Mathematics Competencies.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF THE STUDY

Multi-Media approach: Multi-Media approach is the combination of various digital media types such as the text, graphics, sound, animation and video into an integrated multi-sensory interactive application as presentation to convey a message or information to an audience (Neo and Neo, 2001). In the present study, Multi-Media approach is defined as an approach where more than one mode of presentation (text, graphics, sound, animation, and video) is used in teaching-learning process, especially with the objective of developing selected Mathematics Competencies among slum students.

Multi-Media Approach Instructional Package: The Multi-Media Approach Instructional Package is the package validated by the investigator wherein Multi-media approach is used to deliver the content.

Competencies: Competencies are pre-determined specific learner behaviours based on a specific objective. In the present study, Competencies are the specific learner behaviours expected by the students of standard six, especially in Mathematics as defined by the Government of Karnataka under MLL (Minimum Levels of Learning).

Selected Competencies in Mathematics are the Competencies intended to develop among slum students in relation to Mathematics and they were as follows:

- a) **Competencies related to the Number System,**
- b) **Competencies related to properties of Numbers,**
- c) **Competencies related to Factors**
- d) **Competencies related to Fractions,**
- e) **Competencies related to Decimals;**

Effectiveness: It referred to significant change in Mathematics Competencies between the entry behaviours and the terminal behaviour as measured in quantitative terms.

Traditional method: Traditional method followed by the class teacher at present in schools to develop selected Competencies among the children. This, method was based on Herbatian steps. It was the treatment given for the control group.

Slum: A Slum is a compact settlement with a collection of poorly built tenements, mostly of temporary nature, crowded with inadequate sanitary and drinking water facilities in unhygienic conditions (National Sample Survey Organisation, 2002).

Slum Students: For the present study the term means children residing in slums of Mysore district and studying in standard six in Karnataka State Government schools.

Non-Slum Students: For the present study, the term means children residing in areas other than Slums of Mysore district and studying in the sixth standard in Karnataka State Government schools.

Mathematical Reasoning: Mathematical reasoning is the ability to identify, understand, generate, and evaluate logical, argumentative and quantitative information in order to use them in everyday situations (According to the Dean of Academic Affairs, Office of Evaluation of Student Learning, University of Puerto Rico Rio Piedras Campus). In the present study it is the cumulative scores obtained by the students of standard six on “Mathematical Reasoning test” validated by the investigator.

Intelligence: Intelligence is the aggregate or global capacity of the individual to act purposefully, to think rationally, and to deal effectively with his environment (Wechsler, 1937). In the present study it is the cumulative scores of sixth standard slum students on “Dr Prameela Ahuja’s Group Test of Intelligence.”

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Variables

Independent variables: The independent variable in the experiment was a specially designed package validated by the investigator to foster Mathematics Competencies.

Dependent variables: The dependent variables of the experiment study involved fostering selected Mathematics Competencies among the slum students of class six.

Population

In the present study, the population consisted of all the slum students of elementary level in Mysore district who follow the Karnataka state syllabus. This was the population, to which the investigator wanted to generalize the results of the present study.

Sample

The sample consisted of 40 students studying in the sixth standard. To select students for the experimental group and the control group, ‘Group Test of Intelligence’ was administered to all the students of class sixth. The scores of the students were arranged in the ascending order and students with odd and even scores were assigned to two groups, namely, the experiment and the control group. In order to ensure the equivalence of the groups, further ‘r’ was calculated and found it to be 0.71. Thus group- I of twenty students were selected for the experimental group and the remaining students were considered for the control group. The students of the control group were allowed to be under the instruction of their school teacher while the students of the experiment group were taught by the investigator with the help of a specially designed instructional package based on Multimedia approach. Thus, the investigator employed the purposive sampling method in order to select the sample for the experimental study.

TOOLS EMPLOYED

The facilitative tool was used in the Experiment Study, i.e., a **Multimedia Instructional Package** based on the Multimedia Approach to develop Mathematics Competencies among the slum students of class Six. The tools used at the Pre-test/treatment level of the study are given below: a) Group Test of Intelligence constructed and validated by Dr. (Mrs.) Prameela Ahuja. b) Mathematics Competencies test constructed and validated by the investigator, c) Mathematical Reasoning Test constructed and validated by the investigator.

Research Design: The present research was experimental in nature involving the Pretest-Posttest– Equivalent Groups Design. This design is considered to be the most effective and true experimental design, which minimizes the threats to experimental validity. According to this design two groups were formed, i.e., Experimental and Control group. The treatment for the Experimental group was given by the investigator for 40 sessions specifically to foster Mathematics Competencies using a specially designed instructional material. The students of the control group were exposed to the teachings of their teacher in the regular classes following the traditional method. Immediately after the completion of the treatment, both the groups were post- tested on the dependent variable – Mathematics Competencies. Thus, the data was collected and analysed through statistical techniques.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

The investigator has used a) **Descriptive Statistics:** Mean, SD and, b) **Inferential Statistics:** ‘t’ test and ANCOVA were used.

Analysis of the objectives

Analysis of the first objective was to study whether there exists any significant difference between the pre-test scores of Slum students of experiment and the control group on Intelligence.

Table 1: shows the Number (N), Mean (M), Standard deviation (SD) and ‘t-value of pre-test scores of slum students of experiment and control group on intelligence.

Types of students	N	M	SD	t-value	Result
Experimental group	20	33.45	6.72	0.0491	Significant at 0.01 level
Control group	20	33.35	6.16		

As the above value indicates, the t-value between the two means of experiment and control group on Intelligence is found to be 0.491, which is more than the table value (2.10). Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between the means of scores of pre-test scores of slum students of experiment and the control group on intelligence.

Analysis of objective two

Analysis of second objective was to study the effectiveness of the designed Instructional Package (Experimental treatment) in relation to traditional approach in fostering **selected**

Mathematics Competencies among Slum Students after adjusting for the initial differences in Intelligence and Mathematical Reasoning.

Table 2: showing the Analysis of Covariance for differences in the post-test scores on mathematics competencies between experiment and the control group.

Sources of Variation	df	Sum of squares	Mean squares	F	Significance of F
Between	1	4747.59	4747.59	43.298	Significant at 0.01 level
Within	36	3947.35	109.65		
total	37	8694.94	234.99		

As the above table indicates, the f-value for df 37 is 43.298 and this is more than the table value (7.42). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and research hypothesis ‘there is a significant difference in the means of post-test scores of experiment, and the control group on fostering mathematics competencies’ was accepted. Thus, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the means of post-test scores of experiment and the control group on fostering mathematics competencies. This implies that the experimental treatment was significantly more effective than of the treatment for control group in fostering mathematics competencies among slum students.

Analysis of objective three

Analysis of third objective was a) to study whether there exists any significant difference between the mean scores of pre- test and post-test of the experiment group on Mathematics competencies.

Table 4: showing the number (N), Mean (M), Standard deviation (SD) AND ‘t-value of pre-test and post-test scores of slum students of experiment group on mathematics competencies.

Types of students	N	M	SD	‘t’ value	Result
Pre-test of experiment group	20	17.47	3.17	20.18	Significant at 0.01 level
Post -test of experiment group	20	46.3	5.53		

As the above table indicates, the t value between the two means of scores of pre-test and post-test of experiment group is found to be 20.18, which is more than the table value (2.10). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and research hypothesis was accepted. Thus, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the means of scores of pre-test and post -test of experiment group on mathematics competencies.

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. There is no significant difference between the means of scores of pre-test scores of slum students of experiment and the control group on intelligence.

2. Multi-Media Approach Instructional Package was significantly more effective than of the traditional method in fostering selected Mathematics Competencies among Slum students after partialling out the effect of Intelligence and Mathematics Reasoning.
3. Multi-Media Approach Instructional Package was significantly more effective than of the traditional method in fostering selected Mathematics Competencies among Slum students.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. Multimedia approach can be followed to help students to foster their achievement level.
2. Teachers need to be trained to use multimedia approach rather than simple lecture demonstration method.
3. The teachers need to be trained to prepare instructional material based on multimedia approach.
4. The text books should give enough guidelines to help teachers to use multimedia approach for different topics of the syllabus.
5. The school should be equipped with apt and enough facilities to use multimedia approach in classrooms.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The investigation has been designed with certain limitations that have been from the point of practicability that is, lost effort, time factor etc.

1. Instructional package based on multimedia approach can be applied to any school subject, at any level. In the present study, the investigator enabled its application to only one subject (Mathematics) at elementary level.
2. The study was limited to foster only selected Competencies of Mathematics based on multimedia approach.
3. The study was limited to only sixth standard Kannada medium Slum pupils of Mysore District.
4. The study was limited to only Arithmetic's branch in Mathematics.
5. Only two variables have been controlled in the study.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

1. The effect of the present instructional material can be studied on non- Slum Students also.
2. Studies can be undertaken to train teachers and educational personnel in multimedia approach.
3. The effect of multimedia approach on Non slum students can be executed with more samples to establish better validity.
4. The study can be tried with other branches in Mathematics like Algebra, and Geometry.

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